

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for TREM2 (Q5TCX1) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

Triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) is a transmembrane receptor primarily expressed in microglia and other myeloid-lineage cells, where it plays a pivotal role in innate immune signaling, phagocytosis, and cellular metabolism. Here we have characterized fourteen TREM2 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While the use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID Q5TCX1, *TREM2*, TREM2, Triggering Receptor Expressed on Myeloid Cells 2, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

TREM2 is a cell surface receptor that plays a crucial role in regulating innate immune responses, including phagocytosis, cell survival, proliferation, and anti-inflammatory signaling [1]. In the brain, TREM2 is critical for microglial activation and response to neurodegeneration [2]. Mutations in the *TREM2* gene are strongly associated with increased risk for neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, frontotemporal dementia, and Nasu-Hakola disease [3]. Additionally, recent evidence links TREM2 to the Parkinson's disease pathophysiology [4]. Given its neuroprotective role, TREM2 is an attractive therapeutic target for modulating microglial responses in Alzheimer's disease and other central nervous system disorders.

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data [5]. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available renewable antibodies against the corresponding protein [5]. Here we characterized fourteen commercial TREM2 antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. Antibodies were selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence (also referred to as immunocytochemistry), enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of TREM2 properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway [6] and in Table 5 of this data note [5].

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cells [7, 8]. The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off [9]. The THP-1 expresses the *TREM2* transcript at $7.09 \log_2$ TPM+1, and a *TREM2* KO in the THP-1 cell line was obtained from Abcam (Table 1). Moreover, as seen on DepMap, the THP-1 does not carry mutations in the *TREM2* that could affect antibody–epitope binding.

First, TREM2 protein levels were assessed by western blot in lysates from THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO untreated or treated with phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA), and using two selected recombinant antibodies (Figure 1A). TREM2 was detected in the untreated cells and levels were increased in PMA-

treated samples (Figure 1A). Secreted TREM2 in culture medium from PMA-treated THP-1 WT was also detected by western blotting using the same two antibodies with no signal in the culture medium from PMA-treated *TREM2* KO (Figure 1B).

To screen all fourteen antibodies (Table 2) by western blot, PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the fourteen TREM2 antibodies in parallel (Figure 2).

We then assessed the capability of all fourteen antibodies to capture TREM2 from untreated THP-1 WT protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific TREM2 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 2) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 3).

For immunofluorescence, fourteen antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the TREM2 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines were imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 4). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 4 are representative of this analysis [5].

In conclusion, we have screened fourteen TREM2 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 5 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications [9]. High-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect TREM2 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study TREM2 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available TREM2 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners. We encourage readers to consult vendor documentation to identify the specific antigen each antibody is raised against, where such information is available.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in TREM2, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. TREM2 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) [5]. Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

The cell lines, primary and secondary antibodies used in this study are listed in Table 1, 2, and 3, respectively. To ensure consistency with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations (where antibody concentrations are not disclosed), antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios rather than absolute concentrations. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) [10, 11]. All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

When cells were treated with PMA for an experiment, that information is specified in the corresponding figure legends. THP-1 cells were treated with 200 ng/mL of PMA (Abcam, cat. number ab147465) for 2 days. 200 ng/mL of PMA was added to fresh medium in both day 1 and day 2 [12].

Antibody screening by western blot

Lysate preparation

THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot.

Culture medium collection

PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~ 36 hrs (2 nights). Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at $500 \times g$ to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at $4500 \times g$ to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were then concentrated by centrifuging at $4000 \times g$ for 30min using the Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were finally supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was diluted in TBST with 5% milk and incubated with the membranes for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

Untreated THP-1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary *TREM2* antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min

with PBS. The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.94 air objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification [13]. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for the TREM-2 antibody screening study <to be submitted>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

Grant information

This work was supported by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's Research (MJFF) (grant no. 18331). This work was also supported by a grant from the Quebec Consortium for Drug Discovery (CQDM), a grant from the Ministère de l'Économie, de l'Innovation et de l'Énergie du Québec.

This work was also supported by the CQDM (by a grant from the Ministère de l'Économie, de l'Innovation et de l'Énergie du Québec).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Addgene, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery, Institute for Protein Innovation, MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Synaptic Systems, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab271147	CVCL_0006	THP-1	WT
Abcam	ab269489	CVCL_B1AM	THP-1	<i>TREM2</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the TREM2 antibodies tested in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab209814**	1018789-33	AB_3095849	recombinant mono	EPR20243	rabbit	0.76	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab318262**	1093350-19	AB_3698360	recombinant mono	EPR26209-22	rabbit	0.53	Wb, IP
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP49413_P050	QC58541-43689	AB_10713350	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB11618**	CPHZ0124111	AB_3698360	recombinant mono	2958E	rabbit	0.20	Other
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB17291R**	CLPO0324091	AB_3657714	recombinant mono	237920R	rat	0.50	Other
Cell Signaling Technology	29715*	1	AB_3698323	monoclonal	E4F5G	mouse	0.20	Wb, IF
Cell Signaling Technology	55739**	1	AB_3095850	recombinant mono	E4J7A	rabbit	0.30	Wb, IF
Cell Signaling Technology	91068**	4	AB_2721119	recombinant mono	D814C	rabbit	0.16	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX637386**	45250	AB_3698337	recombinant mono	HL1738	rabbit	2.00	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX637387**	45194	AB_3698338	recombinant mono	HL1738	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
MilliporeSigma	ZRB2124**	RA2310008	AB_3698371	recombinant mono	HL1739	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	68723-1-Ig*	10026574	AB_3206275	monoclonal	1I11	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	83438-6-RR**	23008679	AB_3671079	recombinant mono	1F4H10	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-51494**	AC4650220A	AB_3093112	recombinant mono	240384B7	rabbit	0.58	Wb

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	HRP-Goat anti-Rat HRP antibody (H+L)	31470	AB_228356	polyclonal	0.8	0.4
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM003	AB_3068539	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Thermo Fisher Scientific	Goat anti Rat 555 (H+L)	A-21434	AB_2535855	Polyclonal	2.0	0.5

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 [9]

Figure 1: TREM2 expression evaluated by western blot in THP-1 lysate and culture medium

Figure 2: TREM2 antibody screening by western blot on lysate

Figure 3: TREM2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on lysate

Figure 4: TREM2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: TREM2 expression evaluated by western blot on THP-1 lysate and culture medium.

A) Lysates from untreated and PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO were prepared, and 20 µg were processed for western blot with the anti-TREM2 ab209814** diluted at 1/1000; 55739** at 1/1000 and 91068** at 1/1000. **B)** 10 µg of concentrated culture media from PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells were processed for western blot with the indicated TREM2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Predicted band size: 25.4 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: TREM2 antibody screening by western blot on lysate.

10 µg of protein from PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO were processed for western blot with the indicated TREM2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab209814** at 1/1000; ab318262** at 1/1000; ARP49413_P050 at 1/1000; MAB11618** at 1/200; MAB17291R** at 1/500; 29715* at 1/1000; 55739** at 1/1000; 91068** at 1/1000; GTX637386** at 1/1000; GTX637387** at 1/1000; ZRB2124** at 1/1000; 68723-1-Ig* at 1/2000; 83438-6-RR** at 1/2000; MA5-51494** at 1/200. Predicted band size: 25.4 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, * points toward a truncated TREM2 protein in the KO lysate, arrowhead points toward a ~8 kDa TREM2 fragment in the WT lysate.

Figure 3: TREM2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on lysate.

Untreated THP-1 WT lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated TREM2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads Protein A or Protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the TREM2 antibody ab209814** used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitated, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: TREM2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

PMA-treated THP-1 WT and *TREM2* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated TREM2 antibodies and with the corresponding fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative

analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used ab209814** at 1/350; ab318262** at 1/100; ARP49413_P050 at 1/500; MAB11618** at 1/200; MAB17291R** at 1/500; 29715* at 1/200; 55739** at 1/6000; 91068** at 1/800; GTX637386** at 1/2000; GTX637387** at 1/1000; ZRB2124** at 1/100; 68723-1-Ig* at 1/1000; 83438-6-RR** at 1/1000; MA5-51494** at 1/600. Bars = 10 μ m. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.